

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOFT SKILLS IN EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGICAL INTEGRATION

Inomkhojeva Shodiyakhon Abdukodirkhoja qizi

BEAP lecturer at Westminster International University in Tashkent

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Abstract. The article discusses Soft skills, including communication, problem-solving, and emotional intelligence, which are crucial for personal growth, employability, and social cohesion. Educational programs increasingly emphasize integrating these skills, though definitions and teaching methods vary. It also mentions that Project-Based Learning (PBL) and technology, like Google Classroom, enhance soft skill development through collaboration, feedback, and real-world tasks. However, challenges remain in standardizing soft skill assessments and curricula. Policymakers and educators must innovate frameworks and teaching methods to prepare students for a complex world, combining technical knowledge with essential soft skills.

Keywords: Soft Skills, Education, Technological Integration, Project-Based Learning, Google Classroom.

Contemporary educational paradigms go beyond academics and cognitive skills. Integrating "soft" or "non-cognitive" abilities into educational courses has broadened learning. Soft skills—communication, collaboration, flexibility, problem-solving, and emotional intelligence—are non-cognitive qualities. Success in life and work increasingly requires these talents. These talents meet individual and social requirements, according to Cinque (2016) and the Indicators Project. Educational academics and organizations advocate integrating non-cognitive talents into curricular solutions. In addition to personal progress, these skills promote social cohesiveness and economic growth (Heckman & Kautz, 2012; OECD, 2015).

Different interpretations and definitions of soft skills capture different parts of the issue. According to Lippman et al. (2015), soft skills are a comprehensive collection of abilities, competences, behaviors, attitudes, and personal traits that help individuals navigate their environment, collaborate, perform, and accomplish their objectives. According to Yorke (2006), soft skills include attitudes, understandings, traits, and practices. These definitions show how soft talents affect many facets of life.

Workforce shifts emphasize soft skills in schooling. Companies respect soft talents as much as technical ones. The Deloitte (2017) survey anticipated that two-thirds of employment would be soft-skills-intensive by 2030. This change shows how important interpersonal and intrapersonal abilities are in a globalized, technology environment. Soft skills development is both an individual and strategic economic need (Balcar, 2016).

Soft skills are increasingly valued in educational programs globally. Countries and educational systems tackle this issue differently, which presents complications. Some educational systems have integrated soft skills well, whereas others are only starting to realise their importance (Cinque, 2014). Soft skills are crucial to education, and this article discusses their definitions, inclusion in curriculum, teaching and assessment methods, and impediments to their integration.

There are three basic reasons to teach soft skills. Soft skills improve productivity and employability economically. The workplace benefits from strong soft skills, which complement technical talents and improve cooperation, communication, and problem-solving. As Hanushek et al. (2015) observed, superior soft skills lead to higher pay and better job chances. Soft talents foster personal growth and social conversation. Students learn social responsibility and community building at soft skills schools. Addressing environmental deterioration and income imbalance involves empathy and conflict resolution (Coleman, 2007). Mental health and relationships depend on soft skills like emotional intelligence and empathy (Goleman, 1995; Goleman et al., 2008).

Educating well-rounded people who can benefit society requires soft skills. The value of soft skills extends beyond personal development and ethical conduct to encouraging favorable society attitudes (UNESCO, 2015). Soft skills education promotes critical thinking, creativity, and lifelong learning, which are crucial for understanding today's complicated issues (Woolley et al., 2010).

Soft talents are valued, yet there is no common definition. These talents are classified differently by frameworks. Touloumakos (2020) identified ten soft skills: qualities and values (adaptability, integrity), willingness and preferences (motivation to learn), method skills (problem-solving), leadership and management skills (self-awareness), interpersonal skills (skills, teamwork), communication skills (negotiation, conflict resolution), and cognitive abilities. This classification shows soft skills' versatility. Education and policymakers may determine student skills by using Robles (2012)'s six kinds.

Soft skill instruction must be integrated into the whole educational experience. Parallel and integrated techniques are used to teach soft skills in schools (Yorke & Knight, 2004). Parallel soft skill activities include workshops, seminars, discussion lessons, and team projects. Instead, the integrated method integrates soft skills into the regular curriculum as crucial to academic knowledge.

There are pros and cons to both methods. Parallel learning provides for focused skill development, but it may be perceived as an add-on rather than an essential aspect of education. Though it must be properly constructed to meet academic goals, the integrated approach naturally integrates soft skills into learning (Cinque, 2016). Coaching, mentorship, project-based learning, and simulations improve soft skills. Students collaborate, analyze critically, and solve problems on real-world projects in Project-Based Learning (PBL). Soft skills and student enthusiasm and engagement are improved by this strategy (Blumenfeld et al., 1991; Thomas, 2000). Additionally, role-playing and simulations allow students to practise communication, negotiation, and decision-making in a controlled setting (Goleman & Boyatzis, 2008). Assessing soft skills is difficult since they are subjective and diverse. Standardised examinations frequently miss these nuanced talents. Formative assessments that promote learning are better. Such programs include self-, peer-, and performance-based assessments (Bennet, 2011; Cinque, 2016). Self-assessment tools improve self-awareness and personal development by helping pupils evaluate their strengths and flaws. Classmate feedback promotes collaborative learning via peer evaluations. Presentations and collaborative projects let students show off their talents.

Soft skills education has many advantages, but it faces various problems. Soft skill instruction is inconsistent among educational institutions due to the absence of a uniform

description and classification (Kechagias, 2011). Soft skills must be tailored to the local culture (Cinque, 2014). Continuous research and innovation are needed to provide accurate and effective soft skills evaluation instruments (Kyllonen, 2016).

Policymakers and educators must take several crucial initiatives to address these issues. First, they should define soft skills precisely and provide flexible frameworks and norms (UNESCO, 2015). Second, teacher education programmes should emphasize soft skills development and provide instructors the abilities to educate pupils (Cinque, 2018). Three, professional internships, apprenticeships, and service-learning programmes with private and community organisations may help students acquire soft skills (Pignalberi, 2020; Tino & Fedeli, 2021).

Technology helps build soft skills. Google Classroom streamlines and collaborates assignment development, delivery, and grading. Interactive learning activities in Google Classroom improve student engagement and learning results (Poláková et al., 2023). A middle school social studies class using Google Classroom may collaborate on a digital museum display about ancient civilizations. Iftakhar (2016) suggests using Google Classroom's discussion boards to investigate, share, and get comments on subjects.

Collaborative learning platforms like Google Classroom boost student engagement, according to research. Discussion forums and real-time comments help students collaborate and interact (Iftakhar, 2016). Google Classroom's flexibility and accessibility help students manage their time and take responsibility for their learning, building time management and self-regulation skills (Al-Marroof & Al-Emran, 2018). In a high school English class, Google Classroom might enable peer evaluation of writing tasks. According to Al-Marroof and Al-Emran (2018), students might post their drafts, obtain peer criticism, and update their work to improve their writing and cooperation abilities.

Technology like Google Classroom is underutilized for soft skill development in PBL frameworks, despite its potential advantages. Many schools emphasize technical abilities above soft qualities. This gap must be closed to maximise technology in education (Poláková et al., 2023). Utilizing technology-enhanced PBL methodologies and best practices to build soft skills is crucial to closing this gap. Google Classroom lets instructors create project-based projects that require students to interact, discuss, and solve issues.

Education should include soft skills to meet labor market expectations. Since soft talents improve adaptation, resilience, and work performance, employers appreciate them more. Soft skills like critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, and creativity are needed in IT fields (Poláková et al., 2023). Modern workplaces need these talents to succeed (Robles, 2012). Also, the COVID-19 epidemic has underlined the need of soft skills in the workplace. Communication, cooperation, and time management skills are more important due to distant work and digital communication (Bonacini et al., 2021). In a virtual workplace, soft skills help employees adjust and stay productive (Poláková et al., 2023).

Soft skills education is crucial for contemporary success. Skills like these complement academic and technical knowledge to help people succeed in challenging social and professional settings. Although identifying, teaching, and assessing soft skills is difficult, educators must provide comprehensive frameworks and novel techniques. Technology like Google Classroom may improve soft skills development.

Google Classroom promotes an interactive learning environment that improves student engagement and learning. Students may investigate, share, and get feedback about ancient civilizations using internet resources in a collaborative project. Collaboration and soft skills like communication, cooperation, and problem-solving boost student engagement on this platform. Google Classroom also promotes time management and self-regulation. Teaching students how to create, distribute, and grade assignments helps them manage their time and learn. In a high school English class, Google Classroom might enable peer evaluation of writing tasks. Participants may post drafts, get peer critique, and update their work to improve writing and cooperation.

Despite its potential advantages, Google Classroom is underutilized for teaching soft skills in PBL frameworks. Many schools emphasize technical abilities above soft qualities. Utilizing technology-enhanced PBL methodologies and best practices to build soft skills is crucial to closing this gap. Google Classroom allows teachers to create project-based projects that require students to cooperate and solve challenges. Active involvement and critical thinking should be encouraged in these tasks. Instructors may use Google Classroom to give constant feedback and create reflective conversations to promote a growth attitude and lifetime learning.

To conclude, soft skills must be taught to prepare kids for contemporary life. Skills like these complement academic and technical knowledge to help people succeed in challenging social and professional settings. Although identifying, teaching, and assessing soft skills is difficult, educators must provide comprehensive frameworks and novel techniques. Google Classroom and other platforms help students acquire soft skills for the current job market and succeed in a complicated and changing environment.

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